

ANALYSIS OF THE PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FIRE-RESISTANT MATERIALS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the fire resistance and physical-mechanical properties of fire-resistant materials. The study investigated cotton- and basalt-fiber fire-resistant material samples, focusing on their strength, air permeability, abrasion resistance, elongation under stress below the breaking load, resistance to single and repeated stretching, as well as crease and tear resistance. Based on experimental results, their heat resistance and thermal shock resistance were evaluated. The obtained data were used to develop recommendations for improving the manufacturing processes of fire-resistant materials. The research findings have practical significance for the metallurgy and chemical industries, as well as in the production of thermal equipment.

Keywords: Fire-resistant materials, local raw materials, cotton, basalt, physical-mechanical strength, air permeability, abrasion resistance, elongation at break, stretchability, crease resistance, tear resistance.

Currently, the production of fire-resistant materials is one of the most pressing issues in our country. The transition of the textile industry management to a cluster system, deep processing of local raw materials, proper utilization of new machinery and technologies, and efficient use of raw materials are among the key factors contributing to this situation. These factors inevitably pose challenges for the textile sector, highlighting the priority tasks of developing new types of fire-resistant materials and expanding the product assortment.

This creates a demand for the production of new types of fire-resistant materials with high-quality characteristics and low raw material consumption.

The physical-mechanical and fire-resistant properties of fire-resistant materials are the characteristics that determine their limits of use.

Among the indicators characterizing the physical-mechanical properties of fire-resistant materials, the following parameters were considered: strength, air permeability, abrasion resistance, elongation at break, stretch under stress below the breaking load, resistance to single and repeated stretching, crease and tear resistance, and dimensional stability under hot and humid treatment.

Depending on the intended use and function of fire-resistant materials, specific indicators were selected to characterize their structure and physical-mechanical properties.

Based on the analysis of the aforementioned data, scientific research was conducted to study the effect of changes in the weaving of fire-resistant materials on the physical-mechanical properties of the fabric.

The physical-mechanical properties of fire-resistant materials were tested experimentally in the laboratory of the “Testing and Certification Center” at Namangan State University of Engineering and Technology, and the obtained results are presented in Table 3.

One of the key indicators of fire-resistant fabrics is their tensile strength and elongation at break. All relevant GOST standard for fire-resistant materials include normative values for elongation at break and tensile strength. Tensile strength refers to the amount of force required to first stretch and then break a fabric sample measuring 20 cm by 5 cm using a tensile testing machine. It is expressed in units of Newtons. The tensile strength of the presented samples was determined according to the standard method using a “YG-026T” dynamometer.

Analysis of the tensile strength results of the fire-resistant material based on quality indicators showed that for the warp direction of the new assortment fabric, the tensile strength values were as follows: Sample I – 958 N, Sample II – 1313 N, Sample III – 1398 N, Sample IV – 904 N, Sample V – 948 N, Sample VI – 1321 N, Sample VII – 978 N, Sample VIII – 1231 N, Sample IX – 1234 N, and Sample X – 1058 N. For the weft direction, the tensile strength values were: Sample I – 1091 N, Sample II – 738 N, Sample III – 626 N, Sample IV – 1032 N, Sample V – 721 N, Sample VI – 652 N, Sample VII – 1012 N, Sample VIII – 838 N, Sample IX – 726 N, and Sample X – 1061 N. The analysis indicates that among the ten Samples, the tensile strength of the fire-resistant fabric is highest in Sample II for the warp direction and in Sample I for the weft direction (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Tensile strength of the materials

The elongation of fire-resistant fabrics refers to the increase in length of the material under the applied force until rupture. Elongation is characterized by the stretching of the sample being tested. The elongation at break is expressed in both absolute and relative units. When fire-resistant fabric samples with a clamped length of 100 mm are tested, their absolute and relative elongation values are the same.

The analysis of the elongation at break of the fire-resistant material showed that, for the new assortment of fabric, the elongation in the warp direction for Sample I was 37.0%, Sample II – 37.2%, Sample III – 33.9%, Sample IV – 34.0%, Sample V – 36.2%, Sample VI – 36.9%, Sample VII – 35.0%, Sample VIII – 34.2%, Sample IX – 35.9%, and Sample X – 34.8%. In the weft direction, the elongation for Sample I was 22.8%, Sample II – 33.7%, Sample III – 36.4%, Sample IV – 23.2%, Sample V – 34.7%, Sample VI – 35.4%, Sample VII – 24.5%, Sample VIII – 33.2%, Sample IX – 35.8%, and Sample X – 23.6% (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Variation in elongation at break of fire-resistant fabrics

At the same time, the highest elongation at break along the warp was observed in the fire-resistant fabric sample of Sample II, reaching 37.2%. The elongation at break of Sample II along the warp was found to be 3.3% higher compared to the base fabric (Sample III). The lowest elongation at break along the warp was observed in Sample III, measuring 33.9%. Along the weft, the highest elongation at break was observed in Sample III, reaching 36.4%, while the lowest was recorded in Sample I, at 22.8%.

The fire-resistant fabrics with the highest abrasion resistance were found to be Samples VI and VII. The abrasion resistance of Sample VI was 45,000 cycles, while Sample VII reached 56,000 cycles. It was also noted that the abrasion resistance of Sample I was 28,000 cycles lower than that of Sample VII (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Abrasion resistance of the materials

In conclusion, the analysis of the physical-mechanical properties of the fire-resistant fabrics showed that changes in the material structure positively influence the air permeability, density, elongation, and abrasion resistance of the fire-resistant textiles.

By using cotton yarn in the warp and basalt yarn in the weft, it is possible to obtain fire-resistant products with improved fabric structure, enhanced hygienic and shape-retention properties, and an attractive appearance.

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